

Potentiometric study of the lanthanide(III) ion complexes with some Schiff bases

R. K. Pardeshi^{a*}, N. G. Palaskar^b and T. K. Chondhekar^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji College, Omerga-413 606, India

E-mail : rkpardeshi1@rediffmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Dr. B. A. M. University, Aurangabad-431 004, India

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The Schiff bases *N*-[2-hydroxy-1-naphthalene]-3-substituted(R)-anilines (R = Cl, OCH₃, CH₃) have been synthesized. The stability constants of their complexes with lanthanide(III) ions have been determined at 30 ± 0.1° potentiometrically in 60% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture and 0.1 M (NaClO₄) ionic strength. The lanthanides form 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with all the Schiff bases and the trend in log *K* values shows a break at gadolinium.

The present paper describes the results of a systematic solution study of the complex formation of lanthanide(III) ions with the Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with some *meta*-substituted anilines.

Results and Discussion

The p*K*₁^H and p*K*₂ values of Schiff bases which represent the deprotonation of NH group at azomethine nitrogen and phenolic OH group were determined (Table 1).

The Schiff bases L₁ has Cl at 3-position to azomethine nitrogen and it does not display p*K*₁^H value. The absence of p*K*₁^H value may be due to strong electron-withdrawing effect of Cl atom present in the ligand. The electron density on the azomethine nitrogen is almost totally withdrawn by the chlorine resulting in the generation of positive charge on the azomethine nitrogen. Hence protonation of azomethine nitrogen does not take place resulting in the absence of p*K*₁ value.

In L₃, having methyl substituent at *meta*-position to amine group, there is +*I* effect, hence azomethine nitrogen is more basic. On the other hand, in L₂, having methoxy substituent, there is -*I* effect. Though the effect is small, this minimizes the electron density from the nitrogen, hence lower p*K*₁ value compared to L₃.

The p*K*₂ values of the Schiff bases follow the trend : L₁ < L₂ < L₃. The ligand L₁ having Cl substituent, shows -*I* effect; in L₂ there is OCH₃ group which has -*I* effect but less in magnitude compared to Cl; and L₃ has CH₃ group which has +*I* effect and hence the above trend.

Table 1. Proton-ligand lanthanide(III) stability constants

Medium : 60% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture, temp. = 30 ± 0.1°,
μ = 0.1 M (NaClO₄)

(a) p*K*^H value of the ligands :

Ligand	Name of the ligand	p <i>K</i> ₁ ^H	p <i>K</i> ₂
L ₁	<i>N</i> -[2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalene]-3-chloroaniline	-	9.81
L ₂	<i>N</i> -[2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalene]-3-methoxyaniline	4.25	9.84
L ₃	<i>N</i> -[2-Hydroxy-1-naphthalene]-3-methylaniline	4.58	9.93

(b) log *K*₁ and log *K*₂ values of lanthanide(III) complex :

Lanthanide	Stability	L ₁	L ₂	L ₃
La ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.64	6.49	6.40
	log <i>K</i> ₂	5.49	5.48	5.65
Ce ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.76	6.66	6.93
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.12	5.78	6.06
Pr ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.84	6.71	7.00
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.18	5.95	6.37
Nd ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.85	6.79	7.18
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.31	6.17	6.40
Sm ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	7.32	7.21	7.29
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.44	6.51	6.44
Eu ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	7.42	7.31	7.37
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.63	6.59	6.48
Gd ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	6.94	7.13	7.10
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.29	6.46	6.45
Tb ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	7.90	7.16	7.66
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.63	5.97	6.72
Dy ^{III}	log <i>K</i> ₁	7.26	7.31	7.41
	log <i>K</i> ₂	6.49	6.19	6.73

Stability constants (log *K*₁, log *K*₂) of lanthanide(III) complexes are shown in Table 1, reveal linear increase of overall stability constants (log β = log *K*₁ + log *K*₂) with in-

crease in atomic number up to Eu^{III} after which there is a sudden fall at Gd^{III} , i.e. gadolinium break. The stability constant value then increases at Tb^{III} and Dy^{III} . Such behavior was found for most of the rare earth complexes with various ligands¹.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log K_1$ vs $1/r$: (o) L₁, (□) L₂ and (Δ) L₃.

The plots of $\log K_1$ vs $1/r$ values of the rare earth metal(III) ion complexes (Fig. 1) reveal that stability constants of the metal complexes increase with increasing atomic number (i.e. decrease in ionic radius) from La^{III} to Eu^{III} . There is, however, discontinuity found at Gd^{III} . From Gd^{III} , the plots shows maxima and minima in $\log \beta$ values of these complexes indicating their stability, which may be attributed to the increased covalent character². It is also concluded from the nature of the plots that the present Schiff base complexes are predominantly ionic in the first

part, i.e. from La^{III} to Gd^{III} and covalent in character in the second part, i.e. from Tb^{III} to Dy^{III} . However, no linearity could be observed in the plots of $\log \beta$ against pK .

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with 3-chloroaniline, 3-methoxyaniline and 3-methylaniline. The products were crystallized from ethanol and their purity checked by TLC, elemental analysis and IR spectra. The metal nitrates were dissolved in double-distilled water and standardized³. All the other solutions were also prepared in double-distilled water. An Elico LI-120 pH meter in conjunction with a combined electrode was used. The Calvin-Bjerrum method modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴ was used to obtain pK and $\log K$ values. The measurements were made at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) in 60% (v/v) dioxane-water medium.

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